

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

¹Yuriy Verves* and ²Lyudmyla Khrokalo

¹Department of Ecological Monitoring, Institute for Evolutionary Ecology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine, Academician Lebedev Str. 37, Kyiv, Ukraine, 03143.

²Department of Physical Chemistry, National Technical University of Ukraine “Kyiv Polytechnic Institute”, Peremohy Ave. 37, Kyiv, Ukraine, 03056.

(Email: yuryverves@gmail.com)

Abstract

A total of 74 calliphorid and 180 sarcophagid species are listed from Ukraine, however in the present paper 48 calliphorid and 101 sarcophagid species, which are known from West Ukrainian territory are listed. One calliphorid species (*Eggisops pecchiolii*) is firstly recorded for territory of Ukraine. 16 species are firstly reported from Lviv region, including 10 species of Sarcophagidae (*Nyctia halterata*, *Blaesoxipha laticornis*, *Heteronychia bulgarica*, *H. haemorrhoea*, *H. rohdendorffiana*, *Bellieriomima subulata*, *Liopygia argyrostoma*, *Kramerea schuetzei*, *Rosellea atratrix*, *Sarcophaga schusteri*) and 6 species of Calliphoridae (*Lucilia silvarum*, *L. ampullacea*, *L. illustris*, *Pollenia hungarica*, *P. labialis*, *P. vera*). 7 species of Calliphoridae (*Lucilia illustris*, *Protocalliphora azurea*, *P. proxima*, *P. rognesi*, *Trypocalliphora braueri*, *Eggisops pecchiolii*, *Pollenia vera*) and 6 species of Sarcophagidae (*Pterella melanura*, *Miltogramma brevipila*, *Metopia argentata*, *M. italiana*, *Amobia signata*, *Blaesoxipha grylloctona*) are firstly recorded from Zakarpattia region. One species of Sarcophagidae (*Sarcophaga jupalnica*) is firstly reported for Ivano-Frankivsk region.

Keywords: Calliphoridae, Sarcophagidae, fauna, West Ukraine.

Received: 01 November 2017; Revised: 28 May 2018; Online: 30 May 2018.

Introduction

Altogether (including present data) 74 species of Calliphoridae (Grunin, 1970; Szpila & Verves, 2008; Verves, 1985b, 2003, 2004, 2005, 2012, 2013; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010) and 180 species of Sarcophagidae (Draber-Mońko, 1973; Khitzova, 1976; Povolný & Verves, 1986, 1997; Rohdendorf, 1970; Verves, 1973, 1974, 1975, 1978a, b, 1982, 1984, 1985a, 1986, 1989, 1993, 1998, 2000, 2003, 2014; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010, 2014a, b; Verves & Radchenko, 2017; Verves & Szpila, 2008, 2011; Verves *et al.*, 1977, 1989, 1984, 1991) have been recorded from the Ukraine.

Materials and Methods

The faunistic data of the results of field collections of both authors in West Ukraine, Zakarpattia (Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village, 48°33'N, 22°26'E, 140-200 m.a.s.l. 16-23.viii. 2014 and 08-21.viii. 2015 in

beech forest; Irshava District, Dovhe village, 48°22' N, 23°17'E, 160-220 m.a.s.l., 08-26.viii.2016, at mesophytic meadows with bushes) and Lviv (north environs of Truskavets City, 49°17' N, 23°31' E, 330-350 m.a.s.l., 2-18.viii.2017 in bushes and beech forest along stream) regions (= “oblasts”) are presented (Table 1). Flies were collected by net. The genera and subgenera of Sarcophagidae are given after Verves, 1986, 1989, 1990, 1993; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006; Calliphoridae – after Rognes, 1991, 1998; Rognes & Pape, 2007. The analysis and generalization of literature data about regional faunas of West Ukraine are presented too. Several investigations of regional faunas have been realized in borders of West Ukraine (Verves, 1979a, b) and its separate regions: Chernivtsi (Verves, 1985b, 2001), Ivano-Frankivsk (Verves, 1977), and Volyn (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009) regions. A level of

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

knowledge of faunas of both families of West Ukraine is moderately low (see Table 2).

Results

1305 specimens from 64 species were collected and identified (Table 1). 16 species are firstly reported from Lviv region, including 10 species of Sarcophagidae (*Nyctia halterata*, *Blaesoxipha laticornis*, *Heteronychia bulgarica*, *H. haemorrhoea*, *H. rohdendorffiana*, *Bellieriomima subulata*, *Liopygia argyrostoma*, *Kramerea schuetzei*, *Rosellea aratrix*, *Sarcophaga schusteri*) and 6 species of Calliphoridae (*Lucilia silvarum*, *L. ampullacea*, *L. illustris*, *Pollenia hungarica*, *P. labialis*, *P. vera*). 7 species of Calliphoridae (*Lucilia illustris*, *Protocalliphora azurea*, *P. proxima*, *P. rognesi*, *Trypocalliphora braueri*, *Eggisops pecchiolii*, *Pollenia vera*) and 6 species of Sarcophagidae (*Pterella melanura*, *Miltogramma brevipila*, *Metopia argentata*, *M. italiana*, *Amobia signata*, *Blaesoxipha grylloctona*) are firstly recorded from Zakarpattia region. One species of Sarcophagidae (*Sarcophaga jupalnica*) is firstly reported for Ivano-Frankivsk region. One species, *Eggisops pecchiolii*, is firstly reported from Ukraine. As a result, the quantity of Ukrainian species of Calliphoridae grew to 74 correspondently. The lists of recorded regional species are essentially widened: for Lviv region - Sarcophagidae (from 30 to 41) and Calliphoridae (from 9 to 15); for Zakarpattia region - Sarcophagidae (from 73 to 79) and Calliphoridae (from 28 to 34). One species of sarcophagids is firstly found in Ivano-Frankivsk region (its number of species grew to 62).

The check lists of species of Calliphoridae and species of Sarcophagidae from different regions of West Ukraine according to analysis of literature data and original collections of authors are given below.

Calliphoridae

1. *Bellardia bayeri* (Jacentkovský, 1937). "East Carpathians" (Grunin, 1970); Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Grunin, 1970; Schumann, 1974; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Lviv region (Schumann, 1974; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010), Zakarpattia region (Schumann, 1974; Verves &

Khrokalo, 2010): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005).

2. *B. pandia* (Walker, 1849). Chernivtsi region (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010), Vyzhnytsya district, Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Khmelnytskyi region (Grunin, 1970; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Volyn region: Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia (Grunin, 1970; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010).

3. *B. polita* (Mik, 1884). Zakarpattia: environs of Mukacheve city (Verves, 1985b).

4. *B. stricta* (Villeneuve, 1926). Chernivtsi region (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Khotyn town (Verves, 1985); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Khmelnytskyi region (Grunin, 1970; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005); Mukacheve city (Verves, 2005).

5. *B. viarum* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001).

6. *B. vulgaris* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830). "East Carpathians" (Grunin, 1970); Chernivtsi region: Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978).

7. *Calliphora* (s. str.) *loewi* Enderlein, 1903. Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region: Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010).

8. *C.* (s. str.) *uralensis* Villeneuve, 1922. Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Putila district, Shepit village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Volyn region

(Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Lutsk (Khanina & Khvesik, 1963); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Mukacheve district, Siniak village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Uzhhorod (Moskaletz, 1960).

9. *C. (s. str.) vicina* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830. Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Putila district, Shepit village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Zaleshchyky town (Verves, 2005); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959); Lviv region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Ternopil region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959); Volyn region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Lutsk (Khanina & Khvesik, 1963); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region: Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Uzhhorod (Moskaletz, 1960).

10. *C. (s. str.) vomitoria* (Linnaeus, 1758). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Putila district, Shepit village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Ivano-Frankivsk region: Rozhnyativ district, Mshana river valley (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Khmelnytskyi region (Belke, 1859); Lviv region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Zhidachiv town (Verves, 2005); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region: Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Mukacheve district, Siniak village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Uzhhorod (Moskaletz, 1960).

11. *C. (Steringomyia) stelviana* (Brauer & Bergenstamm, 1891). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001).

12. *C. (S.) subalpina* (Ringdahl, 1931). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009).

13. *Cynomya mortuorum* (Linnaeus, 1761). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Khotyn town (Verves, 1985); Putila district,

Shepit village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region: Rozhnyativ district, Mshana river valley (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010).

14. *Onesia austriaca* Villeneuve, 1920. “East Carpathians” (Grunin, 1970); Chernivtsi region: Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Putila district, Shepit village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Ivano-Frankivsk region: Kosiv district, Gorod village (Verves, 1985b, 2005); Zakarpattia region: Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005); Mukacheve district, Siniak village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978).

15. *O. kowarzi* Villeneuve, 1920. Zakarpattia region: Mukacheve district, Siniak village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978).

16. *Lucilia (Bufolucilia) bufonivora* Moniez, 1876. Ternopil region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010).

17. *L. (B.) silvarum* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Putila district, Shepit village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region: Rozhnyativ district, Mshana river valley (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Uzhhorod (Moskaletz, 1960).

18. *L. (s. str.) ampullacea* Villeneuve, 1922. Zakarpattia region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005).

19. *L. (s. str.) caesar* (Linnaeus, 1758). Chernivtsi region (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Zaleshchyky town (Verves, 2005); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Khmelnytskyi region (Belke, 1859; Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959); Lviv region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959); Ternopil region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959); Volyn region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Lutsk (Khanina & Khvesik, 1963); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009);

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

Zakarpattia region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Uzhhorod (Moskaletz, 1960).

20. *L. (s. str.) illustris* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Khmelnytskyi region (Belke, 1859); Volyn region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Lutsk (Khanina & Khvesik, 1963); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region: Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010).

21. *L. (s. str.) magnicornis* (Siebke, 1863). Khmelnytskyi region (Belke, 1859).

22. *L. (Phaenicia) regalis* (Meigen, 1826). Firstly recorded for West Ukraine.

23. *L. (P.) richardsi* Collin, 1926. Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b).

24. *L. (P.) sericata* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Khmelnytskyi region (Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Lviv region (Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Ternopil region (Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Lutsk (Khanina & Khvesik, 1963); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region: Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Uzhhorod (Moskaletz, 1960).

25. *Eggisops pecchiolii* Rondani, 1862. Firstly recorded for Ukraine.

26. *Melinda gentilis* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830. Chernivtsi region: Putila district, Shepit village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1985b); Deliatyn town (Verves, 1985b); Lviv region (Grunin, 1970); Zakarpattia region: Mukacheve city (Verves, 2005); Mukacheve district, Siniak village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978).

27. *M. viridicyanea* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830). Chernivtsi region (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b, 2005); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Kosiv district, Rozhniv village (Verves, 2005); Volyn region: Shatsk district,

environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005).

28. *Chrysomya albiceps* (Wiedemann, 1819). Zakarpattia region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Mezhygiria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2004).

29. *Phormia regina* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Khotyn district, Stavchany village (Verves, 2005); Zaleshchyky town (Verves, 2005); Khmelnytskyi region (Belke, 1859); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Uzhhorod (Moskaletz, 1960).

30. *Protocalliphora azurea* (Fallén, 1817). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009).

31. *P. proxima* Grunin, 1966. Volyn region: Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009).

32. *P. rognesi* Thompson & Pont, 1993. Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009).

33. *Protophormia terraenavae* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959); Lviv region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Viktorov-Nabokov, 1959); Volyn region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Lutsk (Khanina & Khvesik, 1963); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Uzhhorod (Moskaletz, 1960).

34. *Trypocalliphora braueri* (Hendel, 1901). Chernivtsi region: Vyzhnytsya district, Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978).

35. *Pollenia amentaria* (Scopoli, 1763). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010): Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978);

Lviv region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiyaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattya region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Mezigiaria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005).

36. *P. angustigena* Wainwright, 1940. Zakarpattya region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Mezigiaria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005).

37. *P. dasypoda* Portschinsky, 1881. Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Khotyn town (Verves, 2005); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001).

38. *P. griseotomentosa* (Jacentkovský, 1944). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Khmelnytskyi region: Chemerivtsi district, Chorna village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Slavuta city (Verves, 2005); Zakarpattya region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Mezigiaria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005).

39. *P. hungarica* Rognes, 1987. Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2005); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiyaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattya region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Mezigiaria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005).

40. *P. labialis* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863. Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Putila district, Shepit village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiyaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattya region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Mezigiaria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005).

41. *P. pediculata* Macquart, 1834. Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; Verves, 2012); Deliatyn town (Verves, 2005); Lviv region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010; Verves, 2012); Ternopil region (Verves, 2005), Zakarpattya region (Verves, 2010).

42. *P. ponti* Rognes, 1991. Chernivtsi region: Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001).

43. *P. rudis* (Fabricius, 1794). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district,

Chernivka village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Putila district, Shepit village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Khmelnytskyi region (Belke, 1859); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiyaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattya region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Mezigiaria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005).

44. *P. vagabunda* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Zakarpattya region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Mezigiaria district, Kolochava village (Verves, 2005).

45. *P. vera* Jacentkovský, 1936. “East Carpathians” (Grunin, 1970); Chernivtsi region: Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Skufyin & Khitzova, 1978).

46. *P. viatica* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830. Chernivtsi region: Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001).

47. *Eurychaeta muscaria* (Meigen, 1926). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Khmelnytskyi region (Belke, 1859); Ternopil region: Zalishchyky town (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010).

48. *E. palpalis* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2010); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiyaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattya region (Verves, 1998, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo, 2010).

Sarcophagidae

1. *Macronychia* (s. str.) *striginervis* (Zetterstedt, 1838). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006, 2014a); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006, 2014a); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006, 2014a); Zakarpattya region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006, 2014a).

2. *M. (Moschusa) agrestis* (Fallén, 1810). Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

3. *M. (M.) griseola* (Fallén, 1820). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006, 2014a); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006, 2014a); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006, 2014a); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006, 2014a); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006, 2014a).
4. *M. (M.) polyodon* (Meigen, 1824). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998); Lviv region (Verves, 1998): Busk district, Krasne station (Verves & Khrokalo, 2006); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006); Volyn region (Verves, 1982); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2006, 2014a).
5. *Senotainia (Arrenopus) albifrons* (Rondani, 1859). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
6. *S. (s. str.) conica* (Fallén, 1810). Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
7. *Pterella grisea* (Meigen, 1824). Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a), Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
8. *P. melanura* (Meigen, 1824). Khmelnytskyi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
9. *Miltogramma brevipila* Villeneuve, 1911. Firstly recorded for West Ukraine.
10. *M. germari* Meigen, 1824. Rivne region: Dibrovytzia town (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
11. *M. oestracea* (Fallén, 1820). Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
12. *M. punctata* Meigen, 1824. Khmelnytskyi region (Draber-Mońko, 1973; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Ternopil (Draber-Mońko, 1973).
13. *Miltogrammidium rutilans* (Meigen, 1824). Khmelnytskyi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
14. *Metopia argentata* Macquart, 1850. Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Lviv region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
15. *M. argyrocephala* Meigen, 1824. Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
16. *M. campestris* (Fallén, 1810). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
17. *M. grandii* Venturi, 1953. Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
18. *M. italiana* Pape, 1985. Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
19. *M. staegeri* Rondani, 1859. Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
20. *Hilarella hilarella* (Zetterstedt, 1844). Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
21. *H. stictica* (Meigen, 1830). Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
22. *Paragusia elegantula* (Zetterstedt, 1844). Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).
23. *Taxigramma heteroneura* (Meigen, 1830). Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a):

Yuriy Verves and Lyudmyla Khrokalo

Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).

24. *Amobia signata* (Meigen, 1824). Firstly recorded for West Ukraine.

25. *Nyctia halterata* (Panzer, 1798). Chernivtsi region: Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).

26. *Agria affinis* (Fallén, 1817). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).

27. *A. mamillata* (Pandellé, 1896). Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Zakarpattia (Verves, 1982; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).

28. *Brachicoma devia* (Fallén, 1820). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Lviv region (Verves, 1982, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Mukacheve district, Syniak village (Khitzova, 1976).

29. *Sarcophila latifrons* (Fallén, 1817). Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Shatsk district,

environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).

30. *S. meridionalis* Verves, 1982. Khmelnytskyi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).

31. *Wohlfahrtia magnifica* (Schiner, 1862). Zakarpattia region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).

32. *W. meigeni* (Schiner, 1862). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014a).

33. *Sarcotachinella sinuata* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region: Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998); Volyn region (Verves, 1998); Zakarpattia (Verves, 1998): Rakhiv (Verves, 1974).

34. *Blaesoxipha grylloctona* Löw, 1861. Firstly recorded for West Ukraine.

35. *B. laticornis* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Rakhiv (Verves, 1974).

36. *B. redempta* (Pandellé, 1896). Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974); Merzigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Uzhgorod District: Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

37. *Servaisia* (s. str.) *erythrura* (Meigen, 1826). Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

38. *S.* (s. str.) *rossica* (Villeneuve, 1912). Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998;

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974).

39. *Tephromyia grisea* (Meigen, 1826). Khmelnytskyi region (Draber-Moňko, 1973; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil (Draber-Moňko, 1973); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

40. *Ravinia permix* (Harris, 1780). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998); Lviv region (Verves, 1998); Rivne region (Verves, 1998); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998); Volyn region (Verves, 1998); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998); Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974).

41. *Helicophagella* (s. str.) *agnata* (Rondani, 1860). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974).

42. *H.* (s. str.) *crassimargo* (Pandellé, 1896). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974).

43. *H.* (s. str.) *noverca* (Rondani, 1860). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998); Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974); Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

44. *H.* (s. str.) *novercoides* (Böttcher, 1913). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998, 2001; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region: Kosiv district (Verves, 1977).

45. *H.* (s. str.) *rosellei* (Böttcher, 1912). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region: Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974); Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

46. *H. (Parabellieria) melanura* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998); Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974); Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

47. *Discachaeta arcipes* (Pandellé, 1896). Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Pidgora village (Verves & Kuzmovich, 1979); environs of Ternopil (Verves & Kuzmovich, 1979); Zastinoche village (Verves & Kuzmovich, 1979).

48. *D. pumila* (Meigen, 1826). Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998); Kosiv district (Verves, 1977; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

49. *Heteronychia* (s. str.) *bulgarica* (Enderlein, 1936). Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

50. *H.* (s. str.) *consanguinea* (Rondani, 1860). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region: Mukacheve district, Syniak village (Khitzova, 1976).

51. *H. (s. str.) depressifrons* (Zetterstedt, 1845). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
52. *H. (s. str.) dissimilis* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region: Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rakhiv town (Verves, 1974).
53. *H. (s. str.) haemorrhoea* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977, 1079b); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
54. *H. (s. str.) haemorrhoides* (Böttcher, 1913). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
55. *H. (s. str.) proxima* (Rondani, 1860). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
56. *H. (s. str.) rohdendorfi* (Povolný & Slamečková, 1959). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region: Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
57. *H. (s. str.) rohdendoriana* Mihályi, 1975. Chernivtsi region: Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
58. *H. (s. str.) schineri* (Bezzi, 1891). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Ternopil region: Zalishchyky town (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974).
59. *H. (s. str.) slovaca* Povolný & Slamečková, 1967. Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977, 1979b).
60. *H. (s. str.) vagans* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974).
61. *H. (s. str.) vicina* (Macquart, 1835). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves,

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

- 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009).
62. *H. (Pandelleola) filia* (Rondani, 1860). Chernivtsi region: environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b).
63. *Karovia hirticrus* (Pandellé, 1896). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
64. *Asceloctella (Mimarhopocnemis) granulata* (Kramer, 1908). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998, 2001; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Vyzhnytsia district, Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976).
65. *Bellieriomima subulata* (Pandellé, 1896). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974).
66. *Krameromyia anaces* (Walker, 1849). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
67. *Myorhina (Mehria) nemoralis* (Kramer, 1908). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
68. *M. (s. str.) lunigera* (Böttcher, 1914). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
69. *M. (s. str.) nigriventris* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
70. *M. (s. str.) pandifera* (Blackith & Pape, 1999). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001).
71. *M. (s. str.) socrus* (Rondani, 1860). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001).
72. *M. (s. str.) soror* (Rondani, 1860). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
73. *M. (s. str.) villeneuvei* (Böttcher, 1912). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 2001; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977).
74. *Pandelleana protuberans* (Pandellé, 1896). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977).
75. *Sarina sexpunctata* (Fabricius, 1805). Chernivtsi region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
76. *Thyrsocnema incisilobata* (Pandellé, 1896). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves,

1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998), Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region: Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974); Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Uzhgorod (Verves, 1974); Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Velyko-Berezna District: Vyshka village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b)

77. *T. kentejana* (Rohdendorf, 1937). Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

78. *Bercaea africa* (Wiedemann, 1824). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Khmelnytskyi region (Belke, 1859; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

79. *Liopygia (Thomsonaea) argyrostoma* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

80. *L. (Variosellea) uliginosa* (Kramer, 1908). Ivano-Frankivsk region: Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974).

81. *Liosarcophaga* (s. str.) *emdeni* (Rohdendorf, 1969). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Pidgora village (Verves & Kuzmovich, 1979), environs of Ternopil (Verves & Kuzmovich,

1979); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Mukacheve district, Syniak village (Khitzova, 1976); Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

82. *L. (s. str.) harpax* (Pandellé, 1896). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Logoida, 1978; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974).

83. *L. (s. str.) portschinskyi* (Rohdendorf, 1937). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Vyzhnytsia district, Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

84. *L. (s. str.) tuberosa* (Pandellé, 1896). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region: Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Logoida, 1978; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Mukacheve district, Syniak village (Khitzova, 1976).

85. *L. (Pandelleisca) similis* (Meade, 1876). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolysny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

86. *Parasarcophaga* (s. str.) *albiceps* (Meigen, 1826). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974); Mukacheve district, Syniak village (Khitzova, 1976); Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
87. *Robineauella* (s. str.) *caerulescens* (Zetterstedt, 1838). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
88. *Kramerea schuetzei* (Kramer, 1909). Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Xue *et al.*, 2011): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Xue *et al.*, 2011); Volyn region: Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Xue *et al.*, 2011): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974).
89. *Rosellea aratrix* (Pandellé, 1896)*. Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Xue *et al.*, 2011): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998; Xue *et al.*, 2011): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974); Mukacheve district, Syniak village (Khitzova, 1976).
- *Data “Zakarpattia: Pivtzy” (Verves, 1974) really belongs to Pivtzy village (Chernigiv region).
90. *Sarcophaga bachmayeri* (Lehrer, 1978). Zakarpattia (Povolný & Verves, 1986; Verves, 1998): Perechyn district, Turyi Remety village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rakhiv town (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Velyko-Berezny town (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
91. *S. carnaria* (Linnaeus, 1758). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
92. *S. disputata* Lehrer, 1967. Zakarpattia region (Verves & Radchenko, 2017).
93. *S. hennigi* Lehrer, 1978. Zakarpattia region: Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
94. *S. jupalnica* Lehrer, 1967. Chernivtsi region*; Ivano-Frankivsk region: Kosiv district, Rozhniv village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).
- *After Khitzova (1976), who listed this species under erroneous name “*Sarcophaga bergi* Rohdendorf, 1937”.
95. *S. lehmanni* Müller, 1922. Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo,

2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Berehove city (Verves, 1974); Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974); Uzhgorod (Verves, 1974); Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

96. *S. moldavica* Rohdendorf, 1937. Chernivtsi region (Povolný & Verves, 1986; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Zakarpattia region (Povolný & Verves, 1986; Verves, 1998): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Mukacheve district, Syniak village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976).

97. *S. mouchajosefi* Lehrer, 1978 Zakarpattia region: Rakhiv district (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

98. *S. schusteri* Lehrer, 1959. Chernivtsi region: Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Zakarpattia region: Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

99. *S. subvicina* Rohdendorf, 1937. Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs of Chernivtsi city (Khitzova, 1976); environs of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region: Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974); Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Mukacheve district, Syniak village (Khitzova, 1976).

100. *S. variegata* (Scopoli, 1763). Chernivtsi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): environs

of Khotyn town (Verves, 1985b); Novoselitzia district, Chernivka village (Khitzova, 1976); Putila district, Shepit village (Khitzova, 1976); Vyzhnytsia district, Dolyshny Shepit village (Verves, 2001); Lopushna village (Khitzova, 1976); Ivano-Frankivsk region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Khmelnytskyi region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Lviv region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rivne region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Ternopil region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Volyn region (Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Shatsk district, environs of Svitiaz lake (Khrokalo & Verves, 2009); Zakarpattia region (Verves, 1998): Berehove district, Rafainove village (Staněk, 1974); Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rakhiv city (Verves, 1974); Uzhgorod District, Nyzhne Solotvyno village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b).

101. *S. zumptiana* Lehrer, 1959. Ivano-Frankivsk region (Povolný & Verves, 1986; Verves, 1998; Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b): Kosiv district (Verves, 1977); Zakarpattia region (Povolný & Verves, 1986; Verves, 1998): Mezigiria district, Kolochava village (Verves & Khrokalo, 2014b); Rakhiv town (Verves, 1974); Velykyi Bereznyi town, forest (Verves, 1974).

Discussion

Regional faunas of Western Ukraine are not studied in detail: their review (including the results of present paper) is given at Table 2. The regional special lists present not less than 60-70% of full special list of calliphorids in Chernivtsi (37 species) and Zakarpattia (35 species); of sarcophagids in Zakarpattia (80 species), Chernivtsi (63 species), and Ivano-Frankivsk (62 species). The faunistic lists of species at level 30-60% of full special list is known for Calliphoridae: Volyn (23 species), Lviv (15 species), Khmelnytskyi (13 species), and Ivano-Frankivsk (12 species); for Sarcophagidae: Lviv (41 species), Volyn (34 species), Khmelnytskyi (29 species) and Ternopil (29 species). The levels of faunistic studies in others regions are very low: Calliphoridae: Ternopil (6 species) and Rivne (2 species); Sarcophagidae: Rivne (17 species). One calliphorid species (*Eggisops pecchiolii*) is firstly recorded for territory of Ukraine.

Table 1. List of specimens of the species of Calliphoridae and Sarcophagidae, collected in Zakarpattia and Lviv regions in 2014-2017

No.	Species	Nyzhne Solotvyno	Dovhe	Zakarpattia sum	Truskavets (Lviv region)	Total sum of specimens
1	<i>Calliphora vicina</i>	-	-	-	1	1
2	<i>C. vomitoria</i>	-	-	-	1	1
3	<i>Lucilia ampullacea</i>	-	1	1	4	5
4	<i>L. caesar</i>	22	17	39	80	119
5	<i>L. illustris</i>	-	3	3	8	11
6	<i>L. sericata</i>	4	11	15	39	54
7	<i>L. silvarum</i>	-	4	4	1	5
8	<i>Eggisops pecchiolii</i>	-	1	1	-	1
9	<i>Chrysomya albiceps</i>	2	4	6	-	6
10	<i>Protocalliphora azurea</i>	-	2	2	-	4
11	<i>P. proxima</i>	-	1	1	-	1
12	<i>P. rognesi</i>	-	3	3	-	3
13	<i>Trypocalliphora braueri</i>	1	-	1	-	1
14	<i>Pollenia hungarica</i>	8	1	9	2	11
15	<i>P. labialis</i>	-	-	-	1	1
16	<i>P. pediculata</i>	11	11	22	6	28
17	<i>P. rudis</i>	5	2	7	-	7
18	<i>P. vera</i>	11	5	16	1*	17
18	Calliphoridae	64	66	130	134	264
19	<i>Macronychia polyodon</i>	-	2	2	-	2
20	<i>Senotainia conica</i>	-	1	1	1	2

Yuriy Verves and Lyudmyla Khrokalo

21	<i>Amobia signata</i>	-	1	1*	-	1
22	<i>Miltogramma brevipila</i>	-	1	1*	-	1
23	<i>Pterella melanura</i>	1	-	1*	-	1
24	<i>Metopia argentata</i>	3	-	3*	-	3
25	<i>M. argyrocephala</i>	-	-	-	1	1
26	<i>M. campestris</i>	-	1	1	-	1
27	<i>M. italiana</i>	1	-	1*	-	1
27	<i>Nyctia halterata</i>	-	-	-	18*	18
29	<i>Sarcophila latifrons</i>	-	1	1	-	1
30	<i>Blaesoxipha grylloctona</i>	-	13	13*	-	13
31	<i>B. laticornis</i>	-	1	1	1*	2
32	<i>B. redempta</i>	1	6	7	-	7
33	<i>Ravinia pernix</i>	1	-	1	-	1
34	<i>Helicophagella melanura</i>	2	6	8	20	28
35	<i>H. agnata</i>	-	2	2	-	2
36	<i>H. noverca</i>	2	23	25	-	25
37	<i>Heteronychia bulgarica</i>	-	-	-	1*	1
38	<i>H. depressifrons</i>	1	4	5	-	5
39	<i>H. haemorrhoea</i>	-	2	2	2*	4
40	<i>H. haemorrhoides</i>	-	1	1	5	6
41	<i>H. proxima</i>	5	10	15	13	28
42	<i>H. rohdendoriana</i>	-	-	-	2*	2
43	<i>H. vagans</i>	-	4	4	6	10
44	<i>Karovia hirticrus</i>	-	1	1	-	1
45	<i>Bellieriomima subulata</i>	-	9	9	1*	10

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

46	<i>Myorhina nigriventris</i>	1	1	2	-	2
47	<i>Sarina sexpunctata</i>	1	-	1	-	1
48	<i>Thyrsocnema incisilobata</i>	2	28	30	5	35
49	<i>Bercaea africa</i>	-	1	1	-	1
50	<i>Liopygia argyrostoma</i>	-	4	4	3*	7
51	<i>Liosarcophaga emdeni</i>	11	15	26	-	26
52	<i>L. tuberosa</i>	-	4	4	-	4
53	<i>L. similis</i>	4	24	28	1	29
54	<i>Parasarcophaga albiceps</i>	2	2	4	2	6
55	<i>Robineauella caerulescens</i>	3	-	3	2	5
56	<i>Kramerea schuetzei</i>	1	-	1	1*	2
57	<i>Rosellea aratrix</i>	31	40	71	5*	76
58	<i>Sarcophaga carnaria</i>	28	88	116	66	182
59	<i>S. disputata</i>	1	-	1	-	1
60	<i>S. hennigi</i>	3	-	3	-	3
61	<i>S. lehmanni</i>	30	-	30	81	111
62	<i>S. schusteri</i>	1	-	1	5*	6
63	<i>S. subvicina</i>	-	1	1	14	15
64	<i>S. variegata</i>	34	160	194	157	351
46	Sarcophagidae	173	456	629	412	1041
Total sum of specimens		237	522	759	546	1305

Table 2. List of species of Calliphoridae and Sarcophagidae from the West Ukraine regions

No.	Species	Regions							
		Chernivtsi	Ivano-Frankivsk	Khmelnyskyi	Lviv	Rivne	Ternopil	Volyn	Zakarpattia
1	<i>Bellardia bayeri</i> (Jacentkovský, 1937)	x	x	-	x	-	-	-	x
2	<i>B. pandia</i> (Walker, 1849)	x	-	x	-	-	-	x	x
3	<i>B. polita</i> (Mik, 1884)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
4	<i>B. stricta</i> (Villeneuve, 1926)	x	-	x	-	-	-	x	x
5	<i>B. viarum</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	<i>B. vulgaris</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	<i>Calliphora</i> (s. str.) <i>loewi</i> Enderlein, 1903	x	-	-	-	-	-	x	x
8	<i>C.</i> (s. str.) <i>uralensis</i> Villeneuve, 1922	x	x	-	-	-	-	x	x
9	<i>C.</i> (s. str.) <i>vicina</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	x	-	x	x	-	x	x	x
10	<i>C.</i> (s. str.) <i>vomitaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	x	x	x	x	-	-	x	x
11	<i>C.</i> (<i>Steringomyia</i>) <i>stelviana</i> (Brauer & Bergenstamm, 1891)	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12	<i>C.</i> (<i>S.</i>) <i>subalpina</i> (Ringdahl, 1931)	x	-	-	-	-	-	x	-

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

13	<i>Cynomya mortuorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	x	x	-	-	-	-	x	-
14	<i>Onesia austriaca</i> Villeneuve, 1920	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
15	<i>O. kowarzi</i> Villeneuve, 1920	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
16	<i>Lucilia (Bufolucilia) bufonivora</i> ¹ Moniez, 1876	x*	-	-	-	-	x	-	-
17	<i>L. (B.) silvarum</i> (Meigen, 1826)	x	x	-	x*	-	-	x	x
18	<i>L. (s. str.) ampullacea</i> Villeneuve, 1922	-	-	-	x*	-	-	-	x
19	<i>L. (s. str.) caesar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x
20	<i>L. (s. str.) illustris</i> (Meigen, 1826)	x	-	x	x*	-	-	x	x*
21	<i>L. (s. str.) magnicornis</i> (Siebke, 1863)	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-
22	<i>L. (Phaenicia) regalis</i> (Meigen, 1826) ²	-	-	-	-	x*	-	-	-
23	<i>L. (P.) richardsi</i> Collin, 1926	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
24	<i>L. (P.) sericata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x
25	<i>Eggisops pecchiolii</i> Rondani, 1862**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x*
26	<i>Melinda gentilis</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	x	x	-	x	-	-	-	x
27	<i>M. viridicyanea</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	x	x	-	-	-	-	x	x
28	<i>Chrysomya albiceps</i> (Wiedemann, 1819)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
29	<i>Phormia regina</i> (Meigen, 1826)	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	x

¹ Chernivtzi region: Zaleshchyky, coast of Dnister, 20-21.05.1986 (S. Zhrazhevskiy), 2 females.

² Rivne region: 22 km N of Ostrog, 17.07.1988 (S. Zhrazhevsky), 1 male.

Yuriy Verves and Lyudmyla Khrokalo

30	<i>Protocalliphora azurea</i> (Fallén, 1817)	x	-	-	-	-	-	x	x*
31	<i>P. proxima</i> Grunin, 1966	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	x*
32	<i>P. rognesi</i> Thompson & Pont, 1993	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	x*
33	<i>Protophormia terraenavae</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	x	-	x	x	-	-	x	x
34	<i>Trypocalliphora braueri</i> (Hendel, 1901)	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	x*
35	<i>Pollenia amentaria</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	x	-	-	x	-	-	x	x
36	<i>P. angustigena</i> Wainwright, 1940	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
37	<i>P. dasypoda</i> Portschinsky, 1881	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
38	<i>P. griseotomentosa</i> (Jacentkovský, 1944)	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	x
39	<i>P. hungarica</i> Rognes, 1987	x	-	-	x*	-	-	x	x
40	<i>P. labialis</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863	x	-	-	x*	-	-	x	x
41	<i>P. pediculata</i> Macquart, 1834	-	x	-	x	-	x	-	x
42	<i>P. ponti</i> Rognes, 1991	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
43	<i>P. rudis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	x	x	x	-	-	-	x	x
44	<i>P. vagabunda</i> (Meigen, 1826)	x	-	-	-	-	-	x	x
45	<i>P. vera</i> Jacentkovský, 1936	x	-	-	x*	-	-	-	x*
46	<i>P. viatica</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
47	<i>Eurychaeta muscaria</i> (Meigen, 1926)	x	-	x	-	-	x	-	-
48	<i>E. palpalis</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	x	x	-	-	-	-	x	x

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

Calliphoridae		37	12	13	15	2	6	23	35
1	<i>Macronychia</i> (s. str.) <i>striginervis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	-	x	-	x	x	-	-	x
2	<i>M. (Moschusa) agrestis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-
3	<i>M. (M.) griseola</i> (Fallén, 1820)	x	x	-	x	x	x	-	x
4	<i>M. (M.) polyodon</i> (Meigen, 1824)	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
5	<i>Senotainia</i> (<i>Arrenopus</i>) <i>albifrons</i> (Rondani, 1859)	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
6	<i>S.</i> (s. str.) <i>conica</i> (Fallén, 1810)	-	x	-	x	-	x	x	x
7	<i>Pterella grisea</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	x	x	-	-	x	-	x
8	<i>P. melanura</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	x*
9	<i>Miltogramma brevipila</i> Villeneuve, 1911	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x*
10	<i>M. germari</i> Meigen, 1824	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-
11	<i>M. oestracea</i> (Fallén, 1820)	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-
12	<i>M. punctata</i> Meigen, 1824	-	-	x	-	-	x	-	-
13	<i>Miltogrammidium rutilans</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-
14	<i>Metopia argentata</i> Macquart, 1850	-	x	-	x	-	-	-	x*
15	<i>M. argyrocephala</i> Meigen, 1824	x	x	-	x	-	x	-	x
16	<i>M. campestris</i> (Fallén, 1810)	x	x	x	x	-	-	x	x
17	<i>M. grandii</i> Venturi, 1953	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
18	<i>M. italiana</i> Pape, 1985	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	x*
19	<i>M. staegeri</i> Rondani, 1859	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	x

Yuriy Verves and Lyudmyla Khrokalo

20	<i>Hilarella hilarella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
21	<i>H. stictica</i> (Meigen, 1830)	-	-	-	X	-	X	-	-
22	<i>Paragusia elegantula</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-
23	<i>Taxigramma heteroneura</i> (Meigen, 1830)	-	-	-	X	-	X	X	X
24	<i>Amobia signata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X*
25	<i>Nyctia halterata</i> (Panzer, 1798)	X	X	X	X*	-	X	-	X
26	<i>Agria affinis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	X	X	-	X	-	-	-	X
27	<i>A. mamillata</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	-	X	-	X	-	-	-	X
28	<i>Brachicoma devia</i> (Fallén, 1820)	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X
29	<i>Sarcophila latifrons</i> (Fallén, 1817)	-	X	X	X	X	-	X	X
30	<i>S. meridionalis</i> Verves, 1982	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
31	<i>Wohlfahrtia magnifica</i> (Schiner, 1862)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
32	<i>W. meigeni</i> (Schiner, 1862)	X	-	X	X	-	X	X	X
33	<i>Sarcotachinella sinuata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	X
34	<i>Blaesoxipha grylloctona</i> Löw, 1861	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X*
35	<i>B. laticornis</i> (Meigen, 1826)	X	-	-	X*	X	-	-	X
36	<i>B. redempta</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	-	X	X	-	-	X	-	X
37	<i>Servaisia</i> (s. str.) <i>erythrura</i> (Meigen, 1826)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
38	<i>S.</i> (s. str.) <i>rossica</i> (Villeneuve, 1912)	-	-	X	-	-	X	-	X

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

39	<i>Tephromyia grisea</i> (Meigen, 1826)	-	-	X	-	-	X	X	-
40	<i>Ravinia pernix</i> (Harris, 1780)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
41	<i>Helicophagella</i> (s. str.) <i>agnata</i> (Rondani, 1860)	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	X
42	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>crassimargo</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	X
43	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>noverca</i> (Rondani, 1860)	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	X
44	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>novercoides</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-
45	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>rosellei</i> (Böttcher, 1912)	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	X
46	<i>H.</i> (<i>Parabellieria</i>) <i>melanura</i> (Meigen, 1826)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
47	<i>Discachaeta arcipes</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-
48	<i>D. pumila</i> (Meigen, 1826)	-	X	X	-	-	X	-	-
49	<i>Heteronychia</i> (s. str.) <i>bulgarica</i> (Enderlein, 1936)	-	-	-	X*	-	-	X	-
50	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>consanguinea</i> (Rondani, 1860)	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	X
51	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>depressifrons</i> (Zetterstedt,).	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	X
52	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>dissimilis</i> (Meigen, 1826)	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	X
53	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>haemorrhoea</i> (Meigen, 1826)	X	X	-	X*	-	-	-	X
54	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>haemorrhoides</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X
55	<i>H.</i> (s. str.) <i>proxima</i> (Rondani, 1860)	X	X	-	X	-	-	X	X

Yuriy Verves and Lyudmyla Khrokalo

56	<i>H. (s. str.) rohdendorfi</i> (Povolný & Slamečková, 1959)	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
57	<i>H. (s. str.) rohdendorfiana</i> Mihályi, 1975	x	x	-	x*	-	-	-	x
58	<i>H. (s. str.) schineri</i> (Bezzi, 1891)	x	x	-	-	-	x	-	x
59	<i>H. (s. str.) slovacica</i> Povolný & Slamečková, 1967	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-
60	<i>H. (s. str.) vagans</i> (Meigen, 1826)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
61	<i>H. (s. str.) vicina</i> (Macquart, 1835)	x	-	-	-	-	-	x	-
62	<i>H. (Pandelleola) filia</i>	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
63	<i>Karovia hirticrus</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
64	<i>Asceloctella (Mimarhopocnemis) granulata</i> (Kramer, 1908)	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
65	<i>Bellieriomima subulata</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	x	x	-	x*	-	-	x	x
66	<i>Krameromyia anaces</i> (Walker, 1849)	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
67	<i>Myorhina (Mehria) nemoralis</i> (Kramer, 1908)	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
68	<i>M. (s. str.) lunigera</i> (Böttcher, 1914)	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
69	<i>M. (s. str.) nigriventris</i> (Meigen, 1826)	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
70	<i>M. (s. str.) pandifera</i> (Blackith & Pape, 1999)	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
71	<i>M. (s. str.) socrus</i> (Rondani, 1860)	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
72	<i>M. (s. str.) soror</i> (Rondani, 1860)	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
73	<i>M. (s. str.) villeneuvei</i> (Böttcher, 1912)	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	-

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

74	<i>Pandelleana protuberans</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	-
75	<i>Sarina sexpunctata</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
76	<i>Thyrsocnema incisilobata</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
77	<i>T. kentejana</i> (Rohdendorf, 1937)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
78	<i>Bercaea africa</i> (Wiedemann, 1824)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
79	<i>Liopygia (Thomsonea)</i> <i>argyrostoma</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	x	x	-	x*	-	-	-	x
80	<i>L. (Varirosellea) uliginosa</i> (Kramer, 1908)	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
81	<i>Liosarcophaga</i> (s. str.) <i>emdeni</i> (Rohdendorf, 1969)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
82	<i>L. (s. str.) harpax</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
83	<i>L. (s. str.) portschinskyi</i> (Rohdendorf, 1937)	x	x	-	x	-	-	x	x
84	<i>L. (s. str.) tuberosa</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	x	x	-	-	-	-	x	x
85	<i>L. (Pandelleisca) similis</i> (Meade, 1876)	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x
86	<i>Parasarcophaga</i> (s. str.) <i>albiceps</i> (Meigen, 18926)	x	x	x	x	-	-	x	x
87	<i>Robineauella</i> (s. str.) <i>caerulescens</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
88	<i>Kramerea schuetzei</i> (Kramer, 1909)	-	x	x	x*	-	-	x	x
89	<i>Rosellea aratrix</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	x	x	-	x*	-	-	x	x

90	<i>Sarcophaga bachmayeri</i> (Lehrer, 1978)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
91	<i>S. carnaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	x	x	-	x	x	-	x	x
92	<i>S. disputata</i> Lehrer, 1967	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
93	<i>S. hennigi</i> Lehrer, 1978	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
94	<i>S. jupalnica</i> Lehrer, 1967	x	x*	-	-	-	-	-	-
95	<i>S. lehmanni</i> Müller, 1922	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
96	<i>S. moldavica</i> Rohdendorf, 1937	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
97	<i>S. mouchajosefi</i> Lehrer, 1978	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x
98	<i>S. schusteri</i> Lehrer, 1959	x	-	-	x*	-	-	-	x
99	<i>S. subvicina</i> Rohdendorf, 1937	x	x	x	x	-	-	-	x
100	<i>S. variegata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
101	<i>S. zumptiana</i> Lehrer, 1959	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	x
Sarcophagidae		63	62	29	41	17	29	3	80

*Firstly recorded for regional fauna

**Firstly recorded for Ukraine

References

Belke, G. 1859. Esquisse de l'histoire naturelle de Kamienietz-Podolski, précédée d'un coup-d'oeil sur les travaux des Naturalistes des provinces occidentales de la Russie et du Royaume de Pologne au XIX siècle. Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou 32 (1): 24-106.

Draber-Moňko, Á. 1973. Übersicht der einheimischen Arten der Familie Sarcophagidae (Diptera). Fragmenta Faunistica 19 (9): 157-225.

Grunin, K.Ya. 1970. Fam. Calliphoridae. In: G. Ya. Bey-Bienko (ed.). Key to Insects of European Part of the USSR 5 (2): 607-624. Nauka, Leningrad.

Khanina, I.S. & Khvesik, V.P. 1963. Synanthropic flies of Lutsk city and their sanitary epidemic importance. In: A.P. Markevich (ed.). Problems of Parasitology. Proceedings of 4th Scientific Conference of Parasitologists of Ukrainian SSR: 414-415. Kyiv Taras Shevchenko University Press, Kyiv.

Khitzova, L.N. 1976. On the fauna of sarcophagids (Diptera, Sarcophagidae) of some regions of USSR, 26 pp. Deposited in VINITI 12.10.1976 N 3583-76 Dep., Moscow.

Khrokalo, L.A. & Verves, Yu.G. 2009. Dragonflies (Odonata) and certain two-winged insects (Diptera: Calliphoridae;

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

- Sarcophagidae) of the Shatsk Lake District. Scientific Bulletin of Volyn National University in Memory of Lesya Ukrainka. 2. Biological sciences: 114-118.
- Logoida, S.S. 1978. Growth spurts in the gypsy moth population in Transcarpathian oak forests and the dynamics of this population in the graded period of 1970-1976. Scientific Reports of High School. Biological Sciences (2): 59-65. Moscow.
- Moskaletz, N.D. 1960. To the knowledge of fauna of synanthropic flies in Uzhgorod of Transcarpathian Region of Ukrainian SSR. Medical Parasitology and Parasitic Diseases 31 (5): 575-578.
- Povolný, D. & Verves, Yu.G. 1986. Revision der palaearktischen Arten der Gattung *Sarcophaga* Meigen, 1826 (Diptera, Sarcophagidae). Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Praguae 42: 89-147.
- Povolný, D. & Verves, Yu.G. 1997. The flesh-flies of Central Europe (Insecta, Diptera, Sarcophagidae). Spixiana Suppl. 24: 1-264.
- Rognes, K. 1991. Blowflies (Diptera, Calliphoridae) of Fennoscandia and Denmark. Fauna Entomologica Scandinavica 24: 1-272.
- Rognes, K. 1998. Calliphoridae. In: L. Papp & B. Darvas (eds.). Contributions to a Manual of Palaearctic/European Diptera (with special reference to flies of economic importance). 3. Higher Brachycera: 617-648. Science Herald, Budapest.
- Rognes, K. & Pape, T. 2007. Calliphoridae. Fauna Europaea version 1.1. http://www.faunaeur.org/full_results.php?id=10892. Retrieved 2008-05-31.
- Rohdendorf, B.B. 1970. Fam. Sarcophagidae. In: G. Ya. Bey-Bienko, (ed.). Key to Insects of European Part of the USSR 5 (2): 624-670. Nauka, Leningrad.
- Schumann, H. 1973. Revision der palaearktischen *Melinda*-Arten (Diptera, Calliphoridae). Deutsche entomologische Zeitschrift (N. F.) 20 (4-5): 293-314.
- Schumann, H. 1974. Revision der palaearktischen *Bellardia*-Arten (Diptera, Calliphoridae). Deutsche entomologische Zeitschrift (N. F.) 21 (4-5): 231-299.
- Skufyin, K.V. & Khitsova, L.N. 1978. On the Calliphoridae (Diptera) fauna in the European section of the USSR. Vestnik Zoologii 12 (4): 87-89.
- Staněk, M. 1974. The present state of the Jacentkovský collection of subfamily Sarcophaginae (Sarcophagidae, Diptera). Časopis Narodního Muzea 141 (3-4): 176-181.
- Szpila, K. & Yu. Verves, 2008. *Pollenia bulgarica* (Jacentkovský, 1939) – first record from Ukraine, with faunistic notes on other blowflies in the Askania Nova Biosphere Reserve (Diptera, Calliphoridae). Fragmenta Faunistica 51 (2): 143–146.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1973. New species of Sarcophagidae (Diptera) from the Ukraine. Reports of Academy of Sciences of Ukrainian SSR B (10): 946-948.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1974. Sarcophagids (Diptera, Sarcophagidae) of the fauna of USSR. I. Tribe Sarcophagini (Sarcophaginae) (according materials of Institute of zoology of Acad. Sci. UkrSSR). Vestnik Zoologii 8 (1): 30-37.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1975. The new species of the genus *Heteronychia* B. B. (Diptera, Sarcophagidae). Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie 54 (3): 665-667.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1977. Zonal landscape distribution of sarcophagids (Diptera, Sarcophagidae) in the Carpathian Mountains and foothills. Proceedings of Kyiv University, Serie Biology, 19: 78-82.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1978a. Two new genera of *Miltogrammatinae* (Sarcophagidae, Diptera) from Ukraine and Turkmenia. Reports of

- Academy of Sciences of Ukrainian SSR Series B (7): 638-642.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1978b. Vertical zonal distribution of sarcophagids (Diptera, Sarcophagidae) in Crimea. Proceedings of Kyiv University, Biology 20: 93-96.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1979a. Die Sarcophagiden-Fauna (Diptera) der westlich von Dnieper liegenden Gebieten der Ukraine und ihre Herkunft. In: I.M. Kerzhner (ed.). VII. Internationales Symposium über Entomofaunistik in Mitteleuropa. Verhandlungen: 340-343. Leningrad.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1979b. Palearctic species of the subgenus *Spatulapica* Fan of the genus *Heteronychia* B. B. (Diptera, Sarcophagidae). Zoologicheskii Zhurnal 58 (6): 860-870.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1982. 64h. Sarcophaginae. In: E. Lindner (ed.). Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region 11 (327): 235-296. Stuttgart.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1984. A check-list of species of Sarcophagidae (Diptera) of the Ukraine and Moldavia. In: O.A. Skarlato (ed.). Two-winged flies of the fauna of USSR and their significance in ecosystems: 17-21. Leningrad.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1985a. 64h. Sarcophaginae. In: E. Lindner (ed.). Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region 11 (330): 297-440. Stuttgart.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1985b. Flies from the families Calliphoridae and Sarcophagidae of several regions of Ukraine. Problems of General and Molecular Biology 4: 56-60. Kyiv Taras Shevchenko University, Kyiv.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1986. Family Sarcophagidae. In: Á. Soós & L. Papp (eds.). Catalogue of Palearctic Diptera 12. Calliphoridae-Sarcophagidae: 58-193. Academy Press, Budapest.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1989. The zonal landscape distribution of sarcophagids (Diptera, Sarcophagidae) in the Ukraine. In: V.G. Dolin (ed.). Ecology and Taxonomy of Ukrainian Insects 3: 158-161. Ukrainian Entomological Society, Kyiv, Odessa.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1990. Prof. Hugo de Souza Lopes and the modern system of Sarcophagidae (Diptera). Memórias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz [1989] 84 (Suppl. 4): 529-545. Manguinhos, Rio de Janeiro.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1993. 64h. Sarcophaginae. In: E. Lindner (ed.). Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region 11 (331): 441-504. Stuttgart.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1994. Sarcophagidae & Calliphoridae in Kyiv - 1. Oistros 2: 5-8.
- Verves, Yu.G. 1998. A checklist of species of the Ukrainian Sarcophagidae (Diptera) with a description of a new species. The Journal of the Ukrainian Entomological Society (Kyiv) 4 (3-4): 49-57.
- Verves, Yu.G. 2000. Sarcophagidae (Diptera) from Dnipropetrovsk oblast. Ecology and Biosphaerology 9 (1-2): 122-126.
- Verves, Yu.G. 2001. Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of Chernivtsi oblast. Scientific Reports of Chernivtsi University, 126 (Biology): 163-167.
- Verves, Yu.G. 2003. The flies of the families Calliphoridae, Sarcophagidae and Rhinophoridae (Insecta: Diptera) of Botany garden in memory of O. V. Fomin of Kyiv National T. Shevchenko University. Introduction and Conservation of Plant Diversity 6: 43-46. Taras Shevchenko University Press, Kyiv.
- Verves, Yu.G. 2004. Records of *Chrysomya albiceps* in the Ukraine. Medical and Veterinary Entomology 18: 308-310.
- Verves, Yu.G. 2005. An annotated list of the Ukrainian Calliphoridae (Diptera). Proceedings of Zoological Museum of the Kyiv Taras Shevchenko National University 3: 64-121.

Fauna of Sarcophagidae and Calliphoridae (Diptera) of the West Ukraine

- Verves, Yu.G. 2012. The first record of *Bellardia pubicornis* (Diptera, Calliphoridae) from Ukraine. *Vestnik Zoologii* 46 (4): 380.
- Verves, Yu.G. 2013. New record of *Pollenia vera* (Diptera, Calliphoridae) from Ukraine. *Vestnik Zoologii* 47 (1): 94.
- Verves, Yu.G. 2014. The first records of *Sarcophaga hennigi* and *S. schusteri* (Diptera, Sarcophagidae) from Ukraine. *Vestnik Zoologii* 48 (5): 477.
- Verves, Yu.G. & Khrokalo, L.A. 2006. Review of Macronychiinae (Diptera, Sarcophagidae) of the world. *Vestnik Zoologii* 40 (3): 219-239.
- Verves, Yu.G. & Khrokalo, L.A. 2010. The new data on Calliphoridae and Rhinophoridae (Diptera) from Ukraine. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka* 1 (1): 23-54.
- Verves, Yu.G. & Khrokalo, L.A. 2014a. An annotated list of the Sarcophagidae (Macronychiinae, Miltogramminae, Eumacronychiinae and Paramacronychiinae) recorded in Ukraine (Diptera). *CESA News* 95: 1-47.
- Verves, Yu.G. & Khrokalo, L.A. 2014b. An annotated list of the Sarcophaginae (Sarcophagidae) recorded in Ukraine (Diptera). *CESA News* 101 (1): 7-81.
- Verves, Yu.G., Korneev V.A. & Vlasov, I.I. 1984. The dipteran of families Platystomatidae, Otitidae, Tephritidae, Syrphidae and Sarcophagidae of Zaporozhye Region. In: V.I. Chopyk (ed.). *Problems of General and Molecular Biology* 3: 86-90. Taras Shevchenko University Press, Kyiv.
- Verves, Yu.G., Kotenko, A.G. & Nikitenko, G.N. 1977. Sarcophagids (Diptera, Sarcophagidae) of the steppe zone of the Ukraine. I. Sarcophagids in the Kherson Region. *Vestnik Zoologii* 11 (3): 62-66.
- Verves, Yu.G., Kurasa V.A., Tanskaya T.F. & Zrazhevskiy, S.F. 1991. The brachycerate two-winged flies of the Zmeinye Islands of Kanev Reservation. In: V.I. Chopyk (ed.). *Problems of General and Molecular Biology* 3: 86-90. 9: 46-48. Taras Shevchenko University Press, Kyiv.
- Verves, Yu.G. & Kuzmovich, L.G. 1979. Sarcophagine (Diptera, Sarcophagidae), parasites of terrestrial gastropods in the Ternopol Region. *Vestnik Zoologii* 13 (4): 16-21.
- Verves, Yu. & Radchenko, V. 2017. Redescription of male *Sarcophaga disputata* (Diptera: Sarcophagidae) using light and electron microscopy. *Biologia* 72 (1): 76-83.
- Verves, Yu. & Szpila, K. 2008. *Miltogramma drabermonkoi* sp. n. from Ukraine (Diptera: Sarcophagidae: Miltogramminae). *Polish Journal of Entomology* 77: 57-61.
- Verves, Yu. & Szpila, K. 2011. *Agriella gavrylenkoi*, a new species of fleshfly from Ukraine (Diptera: Sarcophagidae: Sarcophaginae). *Polish Journal of Entomology* 80: 123-128.
- Verves, Yu.G., Zaigerman, A.G., Kozitskaya A. M. & Korneev, V.A. 1989. Cyclorrhaphous dipteran (Diptera, Cyclorrhapha) of Kanev Pridneprov'e area. In: V. I. Chopyk (ed.), *Problems of General and Molecular Biology* 8: 17-26. Kyiv Taras Shevchenko University, Kyiv.
- Viktorov-Nabokov, O.V. 1959. Fauna and seasonal dynamics of the main species of synanthropic flies of the wood-steppe and western regions of the UkrSSR. In: O. P. Kryshtal (ed.). *Problems of Entomology in Ukraine*: 25-28. Kyiv University Press, Kyiv.
- Xue, W., Verves, Yu. & Du, J. 2011. A review of subtribe Boettcheriscina Verves 1990 (Diptera: Sarcophagidae), with descriptions of a new species and genus from China. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France (N. S.)* 47 (3-4): 303-329.